

Appendix 1. Verbal questionnaire to screen for tuberculosis symptoms

Serial #

DD/MM/YYYY

CHATF_FIND_Mumbai Project

Instructions: This form is for all walk-ins at all RAT, RT-PCR and Truenat™ Covid-19 testing sites

Hospital Name:						
Section A: Personal Details				Patient ID:		
1) Patient Name:						
2) Patient occupation		Healthcare worker	Police	Sanitation	Security Guards	Other
3) Patient mobile number:						
4) Mobile number belongs to		Self		Family		
Is the patient currently on TB treatment? ☐						
*If the patient is on TB treatment currently, please do not administer the questionnaire						
Section B1: Questionnaire						
<i>Questions to ask patient as per the 4 symptom complex¹:</i>						
A. Do you have cough for > 2 weeks		Yes		No		
B. Do you have fever for > 2 weeks		Yes		No		
C. Have you noticed any significant weight loss** ?		Yes		No		
D. Do you have night sweats?		Yes		No		
E. Do you have history of contact with a TB case ?		Yes		No		

** >5% loss in weight in the last 6 months which is unintentional.

If the patient says yes to any of the questions from A-E sputum sample should be collected for testing by NAAT for TB diagnosis and further linked to treatment through the NTEP

Sample for TB should be collected in a segregated open or well-ventilated area under bright sunlight, identified exclusively for the purpose. The testing for TB will either be at the same centre or arrangement has to be made such that the sample reaches the nearest NAAT site on the day of collection.

Section B2: Post TB questionnaire for TB testing and initiation of treatment						
1) Was sputum sample collected for TB?		Yes		No		
2) If answer to 1) is yes, please indicate date of collection		DD/MM/YYYY				
3 A) Date for TB sample dispatched to NTEP for testing		DD/MM/YYYY				
OR						
3B) Date & site for TB sample testing on Truenat machine under project		DD/MM/YYYY		Site name for TB test		
1) TB result		TB positive	TB negative	Undefined/repeat test required		
2) Date for initiation of TB treatment (if available)		DD/MM/YYYY				

¹ <https://www.mohfw.gov.in/pdf/1TBCOVIDscreeningguidancenote.pdf>